

NON-TRADITIONAL TECHNOLOGIES FOR IMPROVING ENGLISH CLASSES

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6548162>

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Abstract: *At these days, it is difficult to improve students' interests to lessons with traditional methods. That's why, in the most educational areas is using non-traditional methods for giving students more effective, quality full knowledge. Since the beginning of the pandemic, significant changes have taken place in all areas. There were many difficulties in the field of education, and in dealing with them, experts considered various ways out of this situation. One of the biggest positive problems in the field of education today is the acquisition of knowledge in any case. Therefore, in this article we will consider ways to create non-traditional English lessons in the combined learning period.*

Key words: *blended learning, offline lessons, non-traditional technologies, and internet.*

Teachers around the world find it a challenging task to assess their learners in a classroom environment. It is not a smooth process to assess learners as teachers, in general, perceive it differently based on their academic, professional and contextual understanding of assessment. It might vary from teacher to teacher or context to context; however, we can safely put it that it is a mandatory part of teaching and learning since evaluation is always important to see and determine the progress of second or foreign language learners. As an integral part of learning, "evaluation is not restricted to the context of education; it is part of our everyday lives" (Dickens & Germaine. 1992, p: 3), and we evaluate and assess our daily actions and day-to-day activities to understand how we can improve ourselves. This can be applied to the context of language teaching and learning as well. As language learners are given a different language point to learn and practice in a classroom environment, it

becomes essential for teachers to test learners on previously taught language points, assess their progress, and identify their strengths and weaknesses in order to plan, modify and adjust the teaching method and material accordingly. However, in most cases, teachers have an exam-oriented and teacher-oriented culture in which students are often ignored and learners are tested to determine their next level. This is perceived as a traditional way of assessing language learners who do not achieve the full potential of the learners. Therefore, the literature suggests alternative ways of assessment, such as self-assessment, dynamic assessment, peer assessment, and authentic assessment. Traditional assessment is usually considered a mandatory tool of evaluation that is imposed on teachers and learners to follow a certain set of procedures. This sort of evaluation often lacks learners' and teachers' voice in the procedure which leads to inappropriate and unsuitable forms of evaluation (Mastuno, 2009). Since traditional assessment has been widely criticized for its shortcomings, alternative assessment in the form of authentic assessment, dynamic assessment, self-assessment, portfolio assessment, performance assessment, and peer assessment have been introduced and promulgated by scholars (Chen, 2008; Huerta Macias, 1995). As the role of assessment is widely acknowledged in educational contexts around the world, this conceptual paper takes into consideration the meaning and significance of assessment and its various types that are considered alternative to traditional assessment. This paper also reviews the literature on the significance of alternative assessment tools in the field of English language teaching (ELT) and more specifically in English as a foreign language (EFL) context.

Cause of my choosing this theme is actualization during these time. Its importance that no one knows when will finish of non-stabling conditions. When pandemic powered last year, all pupils, students are forced to learn on online format. Government let to teach whole educational organizations in Kazakhstan half offline, half offline. So it is called Blended learning in a field education. Considering this situation, aim focuses on to create non-traditional English lessons not to lose students' activeness, quietness of knowledge. Teachers can use non-traditional lessons both online and offline. There are more methods, activities which can be used both of them. Teachers are able to improve students' critical thinking, communicative skills, language skills, creative skills, finding solutions themselves, expressing their opinions by creating Blended learning.

It is impossible not to say about technologies. Because, our century is connected with technologies, Internet. Perhaps, people cannot image this century without technologies, Internet. Also, right to say new inventions of this time helped and helps in difficult situations. The undoubted advantages of computers that are present in almost all spheres of human activity include acceleration of information processing in the production and social spheres, assistance in making the most optimal decisions, as well as a banal saving a person from boring and basic repetitive work.

Today, the Internet is the most common form of information technologies, representing the most rapid and giant source of information. Every year the number of Internet users is only growing in all countries. According to Internet World Stats, Kazakhstan occupies one of the leading positions in terms of the number of Internet users among the CIS countries, which already indicates the sufficient prevalence and accessibility of technology and the Internet compared to other countries.

The modern education system involves the use of a wide variety of innovative technologies. The development of new information technologies in education encourages the creation of new software tools and applications that will be able to implement methodological ideas related to semi-automatic or automatic access to educational information, checking the correctness of the results, evaluating the initial and current training, etc. The audiovisual information provided by the use of technical means allows the teacher to be able to make psychological effects on students which are simply not available in traditional education. An example is font size, picture size, color scheme, and other factors. Thus, memorization and understanding of the material being studied is made easier for students.

Modern technologies are not able to replace teachers, students or the classroom; they only create new opportunities for the development of the education system as a whole and contribute to making possible to putting student learning in the limelight. The urgent task of modern education is not the empty development of technologies solely for the sake of developing technologies, but their use to maintain and develop an interest in knowledge and studying within students.

Informational media today are able to provide students with access to non-traditional and authentic sources of information; they increase productivity during independent work. Students discover completely new opportunities for creativity, acquisition and consolidation of various skills.

In the teaching process, one cannot fail to mention such a term as “information literacy”. It is of great importance, both for the teacher and for students. Aspects that express the full importance of information literacy are knowledge of modern ways of obtaining and exchanging information, adaptation and willingness to put it into practice.

At the end, At these time is requirement all skills which written above. Youth are our future, that's why; they must have like these skills.

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